

Investigation of teachers' views on interpersonal conflicts in primary education school units of the prefecture of Pella, Greece

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study was to investigate interpersonal conflicts in primary education school units. The research was conducted using a quantitative methodology with a convenience sample of 52 teachers employed in the Prefecture of Pella. Within the limitations of the specific sample, the findings indicated that there are no elevated levels of interpersonal conflicts in the school units where the teachers in the sample are employed (mean range: 1.52-1.94), whereas teacher–student conflicts occur to a small to moderately high extent (mean=2.17). The main causes identified were issues related to student discipline and penalties (M = 2.96, SD = 1.028), issues concerning penalties and punishments (M = 2.69, SD = 1.094), negative personal attitudes of certain colleagues (M = 2.56, SD = 1.145), and insistence on personal judgments / lack of tolerance (M = 2.52, SD = 1.229). Interpersonal conflicts were found to result in both negative and positive consequences for the school unit. Finally, the most frequently reported conflict management strategies were collaboration (M = 3.40, SD = 1.034), compromise (M = 3.17, SD = 0.901), and avoidance/suppression of conflict (M = 3.13, SD = 0.971).

Keywords: *Interpersonal Conflicts; Primary Education; School Units; Conflict Management; Teachers.*

JEL Classification: I21, D83, J24

1. Introduction

The school environment in the 21st century plays a crucial role not only in the transmission of knowledge, but also in the formation of students' social and emotional skills. In an era of increased multiculturalism, technological change and social challenges, the school functions as a microcosm of society, where conflicts between students, teachers and administration inevitably emerge. Interaction among different individuals within a school organization may lead to intrapersonal, interpersonal, intragroup, or intergroup conflicts (Valente, Lourenço, & Németh, 2020; Ertürk, 2022; Grammatikopoulos, 2022). Conflict can be defined as a phenomenon of incompatibility between individuals or groups with conflicting goals and/or values and is regarded as a social process (Valente et al., 2020). It is also described as a social phenomenon experienced as the result of disputes arising within the context of interpersonal relationships (Rahim, 2001; Grammatikopoulos, 2022), in the pursuit of specific goals or interests (Onyinyechi & Wichendu, 2021). According to Paraskevopoulou and Ioannidou (2017, p. 4) conflict is defined as “the result of disagreement or opposition in the individual (with himself) or between two or more individuals or between groups/organizations” or as “the energy of a person or group that consciously aims to prevent or limit the desired energy of another person or group to achieve its goals”. In the present study, the definition proposed by Mitsara and Iordanidis (2015, p. 58) is adopted, according to which “conflict is a dynamic process that unfolds through stages, during which it either escalates and results in an emotional outburst manifested through expressions of anger by both opposing sides, or is resolved in a mature manner leading to mutual satisfaction before emotional tension intensifies and affects judgment and the ability to address the problem effectively.”

Interpersonal conflicts constitute one of the forms of conflict within school organizations and arise from various factors which, according to the international literature (Saiti, 2014; Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Paraskevopoulou & Ioannidou, 2017; Valente et al., 2020; Onyinyechi & Wichendu, 2021; Ertürk, 2022; Grammatikopoulos, 2022), can be broadly classified into three categories: (a) personal factors (e.g., biased attitudes, personality differences, personal ambitions, lack of tolerance or respect for others and differing views), (b) interpersonal factors (e.g., lack of respect for differing opinions, jealousy regarding others' success and qualifications, gossip and rumors, non-acceptance of criticism, and false or incriminating accusations against individuals), and (c) organizational factors (e.g., failure to comply with rules, neglect of duties, unfair allocation of tasks, power imbalance, poor leadership and administration, favoritism, and insufficient resources). Similarly, Nikolaou (2018) argues that conflicts in schools derive from both structural and personal factors.

Regardless of their causes, interpersonal conflicts entail significant consequences for school organizations, both positive and negative (Paraskevopoulou & Ioannidou, 2017; Nikolaou, 2018). Scholars have identified conflicts as a negative condition referred to as dysfunctional conflict (Spaho, 2013; Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Grammatikopoulos, 2022). The effects of dysfunctional conflict include the waste of time that could otherwise be devoted to constructive processes and, consequently, obstacles to the achievement of the school organization's goals (Onwe & Nwogbaba, 2014; Göksoy & Argon, 2016). Additional consequences include reduced job satisfaction and staff commitment, which may lead to intention to leave the organization or the job position, negative communication and collaboration, stress and hostility, absenteeism, and a reduced quality of education (Onwe & Nwogbaba, 2014; Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Valente et al., 2020; Grammatikopoulos, 2022; Ertürk, 2022). However, conflicts may also produce positive outcomes, in which case they are referred to as functional conflicts (Spaho, 2013; Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Grammatikopoulos, 2022). In such cases, conflicts can lead to the expression of emotions, problem-solving, openness to criticism and feedback, as well as improvements in the organization and functioning of the school unit (Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Nikolaou, 2018; Valente et al., 2020; Ertürk, 2022; Grammatikopoulos, 2022). Hence, conflicts, when addressed with appropriate pedagogical practices, can constitute opportunities for the development of empathy, communication and problem solving, thus contributing to the creation of a more democratic and inclusive school organization.

The extent to which a conflict results in positive or negative outcomes depends on various factors, including the manner in which it is managed. Conflict management aims to reduce the negative impact of conflicts and enhance their positive elements through fair and effective resolution (Rahim, 2001; Gxhaweni & Plaatjies, 2023). In fact, justice, ethics, and authenticity are considered by teachers as essential factors of a good leader in order to handle effectively a conflict (Paraskevopoulou & Ioannidou, 2017). In addition, conflict management draws on individuals' knowledge and skills (Valente et al., 2020; Onyinyechi & Wichendu, 2021). For this reason, Nikolaou (2018) claims that all human resources of the school should be trained in the positive conflict resolution, in order to support schools' growth. Paraskevopoulou and Ioannidou (2017) mention that especially teachers possess the skills necessary to engage with other stakeholders on a regular basis and gain a deeper understanding of potential issues in the school. The international literature (Mitsara & Iordanidis, 2015; Rahim, 2001; Spaho, 2013; Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Valente et al., 2020; Gxhaweni & Plaatjies, 2023; Vinokur et al., 2024) identifies various conflict management techniques, which are presented in Table 1.

From the table below it can be observed that there are various conflict management techniques. However, the existing literature leads to ambiguous results concerning the adoption of these techniques on behalf of the teachers, especially in less urban areas of Greece. Exploring the perspectives of primary school teachers in a non-metropolitan prefecture of Greece in the 21st century is particularly important, as local social, cultural and economic conditions directly influence the nature and management of conflicts in the school environment. In areas outside large urban centers, teachers are often called upon to respond to different challenges, such as limited resources or more closed social structures.

Understanding their own experiences and perceptions can contribute to the formulation of more targeted interventions and policies, enhancing effective conflict management and improving school climate.

Table 1. Conflict management techniques

Feature	Description	Authors
Collaboration	A strategy used for the effective management of conflicts, in which the individual acts to satisfy their own needs while taking into account the interests and needs of others.	Mitsara & Iordanidis, 2015; Rahim, 2001; Spaho, 2013; Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Gxhaweni & Plaatjies, 2023
Compromise	An intermediate strategy based on self-assertion and cooperation, which involves compromise and the search for a mutually acceptable solution among those involved in the conflict.	Mitsara & Iordanidis, 2015; Rahim, 2001; Spaho, 2013; Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Gxhaweni & Plaatjies, 2023
Avoidance	The individual avoids the conflict or chooses to suppress it, even though they recognize its existence.	Mitsara & Iordanidis, 2015; Rahim, 2001; Spaho, 2013; Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Gxhaweni & Plaatjies, 2023
Accommodation	One of the parties involved in the conflict chooses to prioritize the interests of the other party over their own.	Mitsara & Iordanidis, 2015; Rahim, 2001; Spaho, 2013; Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Gxhaweni & Plaatjies, 2023
Competition / Dominating (Forcing)	Reflects an effort to satisfy one's own interests without taking into account the interests of others.	Mitsara & Iordanidis, 2015; Rahim, 2001; Spaho, 2013; Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Gxhaweni & Plaatjies, 2023
School arbitration	A dialogue process that takes place between the parties involved in the conflict in the presence of a third party, who determines the resolution of the conflict based on the interests of the parties, drawing on their authority and expertise.	Valente et al., 2020
School Conciliation	A dialogue process conducted between the parties involved in the conflict, with the support of a reconciler who helps them reach decisions based on their interests and needs.	Valente et al., 2020
School negotiation	A dialogue process focusing on conflict resolution between the parties involved, who meet face to face in order to cooperate without external assistance for resolving the conflict.	Valente et al., 2020
School mediation	A dialogue process conducted between the parties involved in the conflict, with the assistance of a third party acting as a facilitator of communication.	Valente et al., 2020
Social-based learning approach	Views conflict as an inherent element of group dynamics, emerging when individual needs clash with the collective goals or purposes of the group. It is a holistic approach that aims to build	Vinokur et al., 2024

positive relationships among members of the educational community while simultaneously providing tools for the constructive resolution of conflicts.

Systemic approach	It is based on the principles of systemic theory and suggests the imperative need for knowledge of conflict management by education officials. More precisely, a comprehensive analysis of the environment and complex systems can contribute to the understanding of contemporary issues. The systemic approach considers schools as a set of open systems that are influenced by their environment. Changes in open systems in the industry are related and influence the characteristics of teachers	Nikolaou, 2018
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2. Literature review

Various studies have examined the phenomenon of interpersonal conflicts within school units over time. Using a mixed-methods approach in Zimbabwe, Tshuma et al. (2016) identified conflicts among teachers, between teachers and principals, as well as between teachers, parents, and students. Through quantitative research using questionnaires administered to teachers in Achaia, Greece, Manesis, Vlachou, and Mitropoulou (2019) found a high frequency of conflicts, particularly among students. Similarly, Gxhaweni and Plaatjies (2023), in their qualitative study involving interviews with teachers in South Africa, confirmed the existence of interpersonal conflicts among teaching staff.

The causes of conflict have also been the subject of numerous studies. In the study by Tshuma et al. (2016), conflict triggers were categorized as organizational (resource allocation, leadership/management styles, working conditions) and interpersonal (personality differences, rumors/gossip, favoritism). Through quantitative research involving teachers (N = 265) and students (N = 382) in Kenya, Okoth and Yambo (2016) reported personality differences as the primary factor in interpersonal conflict. Similarly, lack of communication, ideological conflicts, and the inability to find common ground were identified as the main causes of conflict in the qualitative study conducted by Göksoy and Argon (2016), which involved interviews with a sample of teachers (N = 57) in Turkey. On the contrary, in a mixed-methods study involving teachers (N = 59) in South Africa, du Plessis and Cain (2017) identified several causes: lack of communication, poor leadership, lack of clear allocation of roles and responsibilities, unavailability of resources, favoritism, appointment and promotion policies, lack of respect and tolerance for diverse viewpoints, failure to acknowledge different beliefs and perspectives, and the spread of false rumors and gossip. A wide number of factors causing conflicts was also found in another study. More precisely, using a mixed-methods approach involving multiple stakeholders within the educational community, Shanka and Thuo (2017) in Ethiopia and Eze and Victor (2022) in Nigeria found that the causes of interpersonal conflict included non-compliance with rules and regulations, resource allocation issues, role perception, rejection of differing opinions and personalities, and unprofessional competition among teachers. Poor communication and misunderstanding of instructions, differences of opinion, lack of adequate administrative skills on the part of the principal, and failure of teachers to comply with rules, regulations, and policies were also identified as causes of interpersonal conflict in the mixed-methods study conducted by Molla, Berhanu, and Demissie (2019) in Ethiopia involving teachers and principals. Finally, in the quantitative study conducted by Igbokwe, Akudo, and Ugwu (2020) in Nigeria using teacher questionnaires, the causes of principal–teacher conflict were identified as the principal’s indifference to teachers’ problems, poor communication, and the lack of clear definition of roles and responsibilities.

Fewer studies have focused on investigating the outcomes of conflicts, with most research referring primarily to dysfunctional conflicts (Göksoy & Argon, 2016; du Plessis & Cain, 2017). Göksoy and Argon (2016) identified significant

impacts, specifically negative emotions among teachers (stress, frustration, sadness), which lead to reduced job performance, low morale, and decreased motivation. Gxhaweni and Plaatjies (2023) found that conflicts result in reduced cooperation, poor relationships, and decreased teacher morale. In contrast, Manesis et al. (2019) found that teachers reported both negative and positive outcomes of conflicts, although the former predominated. In such cases, negative emotions (e.g., stress, anger, frustration, tension), low morale, and a lack of communication and cooperation are observed. In the case of functional conflicts, improved decision-making, higher levels of motivation, innovation, and creativity among teachers are achieved.

Finally, several studies have examined the management of interpersonal conflicts within school organizations, highlighting a broad range of approaches. In the study by Mitsara and Iordanidis (2015), conducted through questionnaires administered to teachers across various Greek prefectures (Karditsa, Larissa, Thessaloniki, Kavala, Drama, Grevena, and Attica), the preferred techniques in descending order were: collaboration, smoothing/accommodation, compromise, forcing (use of authority), and avoidance. Similarly, Shanka and Thuo (2017) and Eze and Victor (2022) identified a wide range of conflict management techniques, extending from dialogue and compromise to punishment and avoidance. Furthermore, an expanded set of techniques, with a clear preference for the collaboration technique, was also found to be adopted in school units in the Philippines in the quantitative study conducted by Halaman (2023) using teacher questionnaires. In a quite similar quantitative study using questionnaires with teachers and principals in Iran, Riasi and Asadzadeh (2015) found that direct communication with the involved parties was considered the most effective technique, whereas conflict avoidance was regarded as the least effective. On the contrary, in the study by Göksoy and Argon (2016), the use of force and avoidance were identified as the primary techniques employed. An interesting finding of the study by Molla et al. (2019) was that most principals do not apply specific conflict management principles and often make decisions without participatory processes. This may be attributed to another finding of the same study, namely the lack of adequate and appropriate knowledge among principals regarding effective conflict resolution. Similarly, Gxhaweni and Plaatjies (2023) found a lack of appropriate communication and the absence of a clear policy for effective conflict management.

3. Methodology

3.1 Purpose, objectives, and research questions

The purpose of the present study is to examine the phenomenon of interpersonal conflicts in primary education school units. The specific objectives of the study are (a) to determine the frequency of interpersonal conflicts in school units, (b) to identify the causes of interpersonal conflicts in school units, (c) to record the consequences of interpersonal conflicts in school units, (d) to examine the ways in which interpersonal conflicts are managed in school units, and (e) to investigate whether the demographic and professional characteristics of the participants differentiate their views.

Based on the above objectives, the research questions guiding the present study are the following: (1) What are the causes of interpersonal conflicts in school units? (2) What are the consequences of interpersonal conflicts in school units? (3) Which conflict management strategies and techniques are most frequently adopted to address interpersonal conflicts? (4) To what extent do teachers' perceptions differ according to their demographic and professional characteristics (gender, age, and years of teaching experience)?

3.2 Data collection

Data were collected through an online questionnaire within the framework of a quantitative research design. A quantitative research was selected because it allows for the collection of data from a relatively large sample, enabling the drawing of conclusions and the addressing of specific research questions through statistical analysis. Its primary aim is

to identify trends in participants' responses and to compare these responses across specific variables (Mills, Gay, & Airasian, 2017; Bacon-Shone, 2015; Creswell, 2015). Online questionnaires were chosen as a data collection tool due to their low cost (or, in the case of online surveys such as the present study, zero cost), their ability to reach a large number of respondents simultaneously without spatial or temporal constraints, the limited time required for data collection, and the possibility of self-administration without the presence of the researchers. For these reasons, online questionnaires constitute a practical and widely used instrument in quantitative research (Sepp, 2012; Creswell, 2015; Faleiros et al., 2016).

The questionnaire was developed by the researchers specifically for the purposes of the present study, drawing on the relevant literature, and consisted of two sections comprising a total of eight questions. The first section (Q1–Q4) examined the demographic and professional characteristics of the participants, namely gender, age, total years of teaching experience, and years of service at the current school unit. The second section, consisting of four questions, included questions examining the existence of specific forms of interpersonal conflict within the school unit (Q5, four items), the causes of interpersonal conflict (Q6, 17 items), the outcomes of such conflicts in the school units where respondents were employed (Q7, 19 items), and the methods used for their management and resolution (Q8, 10 items). Responses in the second section were recorded using a five-point Likert scale (1 = Not at all, 2 = A little, 3 = Moderately, 4 = Much, 5 = Very much). The internal consistency of the data is depicted in the following table.

Table 2. Data internal consistency

Scale	Cronbach's alpha
Forms of interpersonal conflict within the school unit	0.500
Causes of interpersonal conflict	0.943
Outcomes of conflicts in the school units	0.944
Methods used for conflict management and resolution	0.825
Total	0.943

3.3 Participants

To recruit the sample, the researchers employed convenience sampling (Creswell, 2015), whereby teachers to whom the researchers had access were approached - specifically primary education teachers working in the Prefecture of Pella and more precisely in the Municipality of Pella, consisting of 42 school units.

Figure 1. Map of the Prefecture of Pella, Greece

The questionnaire link was distributed to a total of 55 teachers, of whom 52 completed the questionnaire. The number of teachers participating in the study was small, but the researchers faced a significant challenge during sample recruitment, which was the non-response from teachers to participate in the study, due to workload.

The demographic and professional characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 3. The majority of respondents were female (78.8%), aged 51 years and over (36.5%), with 16 or more total years of teaching experience (69.2%), and 0–5 years of service at their current school unit (46.2%). In primary education the majority of teachers are women, as the profession is traditionally considered female-dominated (Gaitanidou, 2014; Economic & Social Committee of Greece, 2021). In addition, although most of the participants have over 16 years of teaching experience, half of them have less than five years of service at the current school unit. This is related to the substitution of teachers every year in many prefectures.

Table 3. Demographic and professional characteristics of the participants

		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	11	21.2
	Female	41	78.8
Age	Up to 30	6	11.5
	31-40	9	17.3
	41-50	18	34.6
	51 and over	19	36.5
	Years of teaching experience	0-5	6
	6-10	6	11.5
	11-15	4	7.7
	16 and over	36	69.2
Years of service at the current school unit	0-5	24	46.2
	6-10	7	13.5
	11-15	7	13.5
	16 and over	14	26.9

3.4 Research procedure

The questionnaire was uploaded to the Google Forms platform, and the link was distributed to primary education teachers in the Prefecture of Pella to whom the researchers had access. Upon completion of data collection, the responses were downloaded, coded, and entered into IBM SPSS Statistics (version 26) for analysis using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods.

The study was conducted in accordance with the fundamental principles of research ethics. Participation was entirely voluntary and based on informed consent, which was obtained electronically prior to completion of the questionnaire. Anonymity and confidentiality were fully ensured, as no personally identifiable information was collected, and the data were used exclusively for the purposes of the present scientific study and analyzed in aggregated form.

4. Results

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 4 presents the frequency of occurrence of interpersonal conflicts. Overall, very low levels of such conflicts were observed, particularly in relation to conflicts with the school administration ($M = 1.52$, $SD = 0.754$) and with fellow teachers ($M = 1.69$, $SD = 0.673$). In contrast, conflicts with students were reported to occur to a small to moderately high extent ($M = 2.17$, $SD = 0.901$).

Table 4. Frequency of interpersonal conflicts

	N	M	SD
Conflicts with fellow teachers	52	1.69	0.673
Conflicts with students	52	2.17	0.901
Conflicts with school administration	52	1.52	0.754
Conflicts with parents/guardians	52	1.94	0.826

Table 5 presents participants' views regarding the causes of interpersonal conflicts. Overall, a low level is observed, particularly with regard to issues related to political views ($M = 1.54$, $SD = 0.874$) and the non-recognition of newly appointed staff members ($M = 1.79$, $SD = 1.177$). In contrast, higher mean values were recorded for the following factors, which constitute causes to a small to relatively high extent: issues related to rule compliance and student discipline ($M = 2.96$, $SD = 1.028$), issues concerning penalties and punishments ($M = 2.69$, $SD = 1.094$), negative personal attitudes of certain colleagues ($M = 2.56$, $SD = 1.145$), and insistence on personal judgments / lack of tolerance ($M = 2.52$, $SD = 1.229$).

Table 5. Causes of interpersonal conflicts

	N	M	SD
Issues related to school administration	52	2.21	1.109
School leadership style	52	2.38	1.331
Issues related to the school's vision and mission	52	2.33	1.167
Issues related to the school's strategy (e.g., activities)	52	2.33	1.115
Issues related to work ethics	52	2.40	1.272
Issues related to teaching methods	52	2.08	1.064
Issues related to compliance with rules / student discipline	52	2.96	1.028
Issues concerning penalties and punishments	52	2.69	1.094
Issues related to workload distribution among staff	52	2.33	1.150
Issues related to legislation	52	2.10	1.125
Issues related to political views	52	1.54	.874
Negative personal attitudes of certain colleagues	52	2.56	1.145
Lack of respect for differing views	52	2.33	1.216
Gossip and rumors / false and incriminating accusations	52	2.48	1.393
Insistence on personal judgments / lack of tolerance	52	2.52	1.229
Non-recognition of newly appointed staff members	52	1.79	1.177
Competition for others' success and qualifications	52	2.10	1.302

The participating teachers' views regarding the outcomes of interpersonal conflicts within the school unit are presented in Table 6. As an initial observation, all mean values fall between the response categories "a little" and "moderately," indicating a generally moderate perceived impact. Higher mean values were recorded for both positive and negative outcomes. Specifically, the outcomes with the highest mean scores were expression of emotions ($M = 2.94$, $SD = 1.178$), lack of communication ($M = 2.88$, $SD = 1.381$), problem solving ($M = 2.83$, $SD = 1.184$), low level of job satisfaction ($M = 2.81$, $SD = 1.329$), reduced cooperation and low team spirit ($M = 2.65$, $SD = 1.385$), ability to examine events from multiple perspectives ($M = 2.65$, $SD = 1.153$), overcoming obstacles among staff members ($M = 2.63$, $SD = 1.237$), intention to leave the job position ($M = 2.62$, $SD = 1.316$), and stress, indifference, hostility, and polarization ($M = 2.60$, $SD = 1.287$).

The participants' views regarding the management of interpersonal conflicts within the school unit are presented in Table 7. The three most frequently reported conflict management methods were collaboration ($M = 3.40$, $SD = 1.034$), compromise ($M = 3.17$, $SD = 0.901$), and avoidance/suppression of conflict ($M = 3.13$, $SD = 0.971$). To a fairly high extent, participants also reported the use of the Social-Based Learning Approach ($M = 3.08$, $SD = 1.118$), school mediation ($M = 3.00$, $SD = 1.188$), and school conciliation ($M = 3.00$, $SD = 1.155$). In contrast, the lowest mean score was recorded for the competition/dominating (forcing) method ($M = 2.31$, $SD = 1.039$).

Table 6. Outcomes of interpersonal conflicts

	N	M	SD
Waste of time that could be devoted to constructive processes	52	2.44	1.290
Reduced staff job performance	52	2.31	1.336
Reduced staff motivation	52	2.17	1.232
Reduced quality of education	52	2.27	1.285
Reduced cooperation and low team spirit	52	2.65	1.385
Low morale	52	2.52	1.321
Low level of job satisfaction	52	2.81	1.329
Intention to leave the job position	52	2.62	1.316
Reduced organizational commitment	52	2.44	1.178
Increased absenteeism	52	2.13	1.155
Stress, indifference, hostility, polarization	52	2.60	1.287
Lack of communication	52	2.88	1.381
Respect for different ideas / views	52	2.33	1.200
Development of understanding	52	2.40	1.142
Ability to examine events from multiple perspectives	52	2.65	1.153
Expression of emotions	52	2.94	1.178
Encouragement of creativity	52	2.42	1.210
Problem solving	52	2.83	1.184
Overcoming obstacles among staff members	52	2.63	1.237

Table 7. Interpersonal conflict management methods

	N	M	SD
Collaborative approach, aiming to resolve the conflict through cooperation with the other party	52	3.40	1.034
Compromise, representing an effort to satisfy the interests of all parties involved in the conflict	52	3.17	.901
Avoidance / suppression of the conflict	52	3.13	.971
Accommodation, where one of the parties involved in the conflict chooses to prioritize the interests of the other party over their own	52	2.60	1.107
Competition / dominating, reflecting an effort to satisfy one's own interests without taking into account the interests of the other party	52	2.31	1.039
School arbitration (a dialogue process that takes place between the parties involved in the conflict in the presence of a third party, who determines the resolution of the conflict based on the interests of the parties, drawing on their authority and expertise)	52	2.79	1.289
School conciliation (a dialogue process conducted between the parties involved in the conflict, with the support of a conciliator who helps them reach decisions based on their interests and needs)	52	3.00	1.155
School negotiation (a dialogue process focusing on conflict resolution between the parties involved, who meet face to face in order to cooperate without external assistance to resolve the conflict)	52	2.98	1.075
School mediation (a dialogue process conducted between the parties involved in the conflict, with the assistance of a third party acting as a communication facilitator)	52	3.00	1.188
Social-Based Learning Approach, which seeks to build positive relationships among members of the educational community while simultaneously providing tools for the constructive resolution of conflicts	52	3.08	1.118

4.2 Inferential statistics

This section examines whether the demographic and professional characteristics of the participating teachers differentiate the views they expressed, as presented in the previous section. To determine the appropriate statistical tests, an initial normality assessment was conducted using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, with the level of statistical significance set at $\alpha = 0.05$. The results indicated that the data did not follow a normal distribution ($p < 0.05$). Consequently, non-parametric tests were applied. Specifically, the Mann–Whitney U test (the non-parametric equivalent of the independent samples t-test) was used to examine differences based on gender, while the Kruskal–Wallis test (the non-parametric equivalent of one-way ANOVA) was employed to examine differences based on age and years of teaching experience, both overall and at the current school unit. The level of statistical significance was set at $\alpha = 0.05$. The results are presented in Table 8. With regard to gender, no statistically significant differences were observed ($p > 0.05$). Similarly, no statistically significant differences were identified in relation to total years of teaching experience ($p > 0.05$). In contrast, statistically significant differences emerged with respect to age and years of service at the current school unit.

Regarding age, a statistically significant difference was found in the occurrence of conflicts with fellow teachers ($p < 0.05$), with younger participants reporting lower levels of such conflicts, whereas participants aged 41–50 reported higher levels. A statistically significant difference was also observed in the extent to which issues related to legislation

were perceived as causes of conflict ($p < 0.05$), with younger participants indicating higher levels of agreement, while participants aged 51 and over reported lower levels. Furthermore, age-related differences were identified in the use of the school conciliation technique for conflict management ($p < 0.05$), with participants aged up to 30 years reporting higher levels of agreement and those aged 41–50 reporting lower levels.

With respect to years of service at the current school unit, a statistically significant difference was observed in the occurrence of interpersonal conflicts with the school administration ($p < 0.05$), with participants having 0–5 years of service reporting higher levels and those with 16 years or more reporting lower levels. In addition, a statistically significant difference was identified in the use of the school arbitration technique for conflict management ($p < 0.05$), with participants having 11–15 years of service indicating higher levels of agreement, whereas those with 16 years or more indicated lower levels.

Table 8. Differences in teachers' views based on their demographic and professional characteristics

	Age	Years of service at the current school unit
Frequency of occurrence of interpersonal conflicts		
Conflicts with fellow teachers	0.028	
Conflicts with the school administration		0.043
Causes of interpersonal conflicts		
Issues related to legislation	0.047	
Interpersonal conflict management methods		
School arbitration (a dialogue process conducted between the parties involved in the conflict in the presence of a third party who determines the resolution of the conflict based on the interests of the parties, drawing on their authority and expertise)		0.030
School conciliation (a dialogue process conducted between the parties involved in the conflict, with the support of a conciliator who helps them make decisions based on their interests and needs)	0.027	

5. Discussion

The results of the statistical analysis initially indicated that there are no elevated levels of interpersonal conflicts in the school units where the sampled teachers are employed, in contrast to the findings of other studies (Tshuma et al., 2016; Manesis et al., 2019; Gxhaweni & Plaatjies, 2023). Even teacher–student conflicts were found to occur to a small to moderately high extent. However, the reasons behind the absence of high-level interpersonal conflicts remain unclear, a fact that could constitute a subject for further investigation. Furthermore, the low recorded levels of conflict could be partially attributed to social desirability bias, as teachers may be inherently hesitant to openly admit to interpersonal disputes in order to maintain a positive image of their school environment. In this regard, this interpretation is consistent with the findings of Saiti (2014), who noted that Greek educators often underreport conflicts or present a more idealized version of their school climate to avoid professional exposure. Therefore, it remains a critical question for future research whether our findings reflect genuine harmony or a strategic avoidance of acknowledging professional friction, reinforcing Saiti's perspective that self-reported data on school conflicts should be interpreted with caution. For example, future research could examine whether the low levels of interpersonal conflict are attributable to leadership style and the manner in which school administration is exercised, the existence of effective communication, the presence of specific policies for managing issues before conflicts arise, the implementation of a student code of conduct, or other contextual

factors. It is also noteworthy that younger teachers tend to report even lower levels of interpersonal conflicts with fellow teachers. This finding may be attributed to various factors, such as the avoidance of confrontation in a new working environment with more experienced colleagues, a different interpretation of events occurring within the school unit, a higher level of tolerance toward differing viewpoints, or other reasons that could likewise be explored in future research. Furthermore, teachers with fewer years of service at their current school unit reported higher levels of interpersonal conflicts with the school administration, possibly due to a different perspective associated with their younger age or previous professional experience. At this point as well, future research could clarify the causes of these differences, particularly given that no relevant studies were identified in the international literature. This, on the one hand, limits the comparability of the findings of the present study with those of previous research and, on the other hand, highlights a gap in the existing literature.

Possibly due to the low overall prevalence of interpersonal conflicts, the reported level of their underlying causes was also low. The factors identified mainly concern interactions involving students where, notably, the highest level of interpersonal conflict was recorded specifically issues related to compliance with rules and student discipline, as well as matters concerning penalties and punishments. In addition, negative personal attitudes of certain colleagues and insistence on personal judgments combined with a lack of tolerance were reported. Negative personal attitudes and student behavior have been identified as key causes of interpersonal conflicts by several researchers (Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Onyinyechi & Wichendu, 2021). Similarly, insistence on personal judgments, in conjunction with a lack of tolerance toward others' views, has been documented in the literature as a significant source of interpersonal conflict (Saiti, 2014; Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Valente et al., 2020; Onyinyechi & Wichendu, 2021; Ertürk, 2022; Grammatikopoulos, 2022). It is also noteworthy that younger teachers tend to perceive issues related to legislation as causes of interpersonal conflict to a greater extent. This finding could be interpreted either as a lack of sufficient knowledge of the relevant legal framework or as opposition to existing legislation due to differing perceptions of practices within the school unit. Further research could explore the reasons underlying this differentiation in greater depth, particularly given that no studies were identified examining the influence of teachers' demographic characteristics on their perceptions.

Particularly noteworthy are the results of the present study concerning the outcomes of interpersonal conflicts. Specifically, the statistical analysis revealed results reflecting both the negative and the positive impact of such conflicts on school organizations, a duality that has been highlighted by several researchers in previous studies (Spaho, 2013; Onwe & Nwogbaba, 2014; Göksoy & Argon, 2016; Manesis et al., 2019; Valente et al., 2020; Grammatikopoulos, 2022). Within the category of negative consequences, the following were identified in descending order: lack of communication, low level of job satisfaction, reduced cooperation and low team spirit, intention to leave the job position, and experiences of stress, indifference, hostility, and polarization. Similar findings have been reported in earlier research (Göksoy & Argon, 2016; du Plessis & Cain, 2017; Manesis et al., 2019; Gxhaweni & Plaatjies, 2023). Within the category of positive outcomes, the following were identified in descending order: expression of emotions, problem-solving, the ability to examine events from multiple perspectives, and overcoming obstacles among staff members. This finding is consistent with the results reported by Manesis et al. (2019).

Regarding the management of interpersonal conflicts within the school unit, collaboration and compromise were the techniques most frequently reported by teachers. The social-based learning approach, school mediation, and school conciliation were also identified as additional methods employed. However, it should not be overlooked that avoidance/suppression of conflict was likewise found to be used to a fairly high extent—as also reported by Göksoy and Argon (2016)—despite the fact that it is not considered an appropriate conflict management approach according to Riasi and Asadzadeh (2015). According to Thomas and Kilmann's conflict mode instrument, "avoidance" in conflict management in school organizations can be either a conscious strategy or a passive stance, depending on the context. As a strategic choice, avoidance is useful when the issue is of secondary importance, when time is needed to defuse tension

or to gather more information before intervening. Conversely, it becomes a passive stance when it is systematically used to avoid difficult situations or responsibilities, leading to the perpetuation of conflicts and the deterioration of the school climate (Riasi & Asadzadeh, 2015). The use of multiple conflict management techniques has been documented in previous research (Mitsara & Iordanidis, 2015; Shanka & Thuo, 2017; Eze & Victor, 2022). Future research could further examine the criteria on the basis of which specific conflict management techniques are selected, such as teachers' knowledge and skills in applying these techniques, the possible imposition of particular approaches by school administration, or their perceived effectiveness based on teachers' beliefs and professional experiences. Additionally, within the limitations of the specific sample, the findings indicated that younger teachers tend to report greater use of the school conciliation technique, whereas teachers with more years of service at the current school unit tend to report lower use of school arbitration. Further research could investigate the underlying causes of these differences in depth. A preliminary interpretation is that teachers with longer service at the school may have developed alternative ways of managing conflicts, or that newly appointed teachers may possess a different level of expertise regarding the benefits of specific techniques, such as school conciliation, either through recent theoretical training (e.g., during their university education) or through prior experience in other school units.

6. Conclusion, recommendations, limitations and future directions

The purpose of the present study was to examine the views of primary education teachers regarding the phenomenon of interpersonal conflicts within school units. To this end, a quantitative study was conducted using an online questionnaire administered to a sample of teachers (N = 52) in the Prefecture of Pella. The analysis of the collected data indicated that there are no elevated levels of interpersonal conflicts in the school units where the participating teachers are employed, with the exception of conflicts involving students, which were found to occur to a small to moderately high extent. Accordingly, the reported causes of conflicts appear to be more closely related to students, particularly issues concerning discipline and penalties/punishments. A particularly important finding was that interpersonal conflicts were found to lead not only to negative but also to positive outcomes. Finally, several conflict management techniques are employed in the school units included in the sample.

Despite the fact that the climate in the schools of Pella seems positive, there is still a need for training in effective conflict management. Effectively addressing conflicts, especially between teachers and students, in schools requires a combination of preventive and intervention strategies, as well as systematic training of teachers. At the prevention level, it is important to cultivate a positive school climate through clear rules, strengthening empathy and developing communication and emotional education skills. At the same time, teachers can utilize techniques such as active listening, mediation and collaborative problem solving, in order to manage conflicts in a pedagogical way. Their training should include experiential seminars, reflection on real incidents and familiarization with conflict management models, strengthening their ability to prevent tensions and transform conflicts into opportunities for learning and development.

Based on the findings, several recommendations for future research were proposed in order to clarify issues related to leadership and management practices within school units that may influence the emergence of specific types of conflicts, their causes, and their outcomes, as well as the criteria guiding the use of particular interpersonal conflict management techniques. It should be emphasized, though, that these recommendations are grounded in findings derived from a study conducted on a relatively small sample of teachers, from a specific geographical region of Greece, and limited to primary education school units. Hence, the results cannot be generalized to a wider population. In addition, the findings are based on self-reported data, which may be subject to response biases, such as social desirability, and should therefore be interpreted with caution.

For this reason, further research is considered necessary using a larger and more representative sample, ideally encompassing the whole of Greece. A comparative study between primary and secondary education school units could

yield particularly interesting results, taking into account the differences between these two educational levels (e.g., students' age, number of teachers, and characteristics of the educational process). The use of a qualitative research approach could help clarify certain issues and provide opportunities for an in-depth exploration of the phenomenon of interpersonal conflicts. Expanding the scope of future research to include other forms of conflict may also be beneficial and could be further enriched by involving various stakeholders within the educational community beyond teachers, such as school principals, students, and parents. Finally, future studies could examine the impact of additional factors not addressed in the present study on teachers' views, including further socio-demographic characteristics of teachers (e.g., level of education, training in conflict and conflict management), characteristics of school units (e.g., size, location), as well as organizational factors (e.g., leadership style, type of administration, communication practices, and the existence of written policies or codes concerning behavior and conflict prevention).

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